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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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EVOLUTION OF CHINA'S APPROACHES TO COMBATING DRUG TRAFFICKING

ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to China's experience in the fight against drug trafficking. Contains an analysis of the relevant law of the People's Republic of China adopted in December 2007. An overview of the related law enforcement practice is given, as well as the interaction of the PRC with other countries in this area. An analysis was made of the "White Paper", which established the basic principles of the anti-drug policy of the PRC, which was published in June 2000, where the task was set for the complete eradication of drugs in China.

Keywords: China, East Asia, Shanghai, drug threat, drug control, fight against drug trafficking, opium, synthetic drugs, drug addicts, psychotropic substances.

ХИТОЙНИНГ КУРАШГА ЁНДАШУВЛАРИ ЕВОЛЮЦИЯСИ ГИЁХВАНД МОДДАЛАР САВДОСИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақола Хитойнинг гиёхванд воситалар савдосига қарши курашиш тажрибасига бағишланган. 2007 йил декабрь ойида қабул қилинган тегишли ХХР қонуни таҳлилини ўз ичига олади. Тегишли ҳуқуқни қўллаш амалиёти, шунингдек, ХХРнинг ушбу соҳадаги бошқа давлатлар билан ўзаро ҳамкорлиги ҳақида умумий маълумот берилган. ХХРнинг гиёхвандликка қарши сиёсатининг асосий тамойилларини белгилаб берувчи 2000-йил июнь ойида нашр этилган "Оқ китоб" таҳлили о'тказилди, унда Хитойда гиёхванд воситаларни то'лик ё'қ қилиш вазифаси қўйилган эди.

Калит сўзлар: Хитой, Шарқий Осиё, Шанхай, наркотик таҳдиди, гиёхвандликка қарши кураш, гиёхванд моддалар савдосига қарши кураш, опиум, синтетик гиёхванд воситалар, гиёхвандлар, психотроп моддалар.

ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ ПОДХОДОВ КИТАЯ К БОРЬБЕ С НЕЗАКОННЫЙ ОБОРОТ НАРКОТИКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена опыту Китая в борьбе с незаконным оборотом наркотиков. Содержит анализ принятого в декабре 2007 г. соответствующего закона КНР. Дается обзор связанный с ним правоприменительной практики, а также взаимодействия КНР с другими странами в данной сфере.

Сделан анализ о “Белой книги” закрепившим основные принципы антинаркотической политики КНР, который был опубликован в июне 2000 года где было поставлена задача по полному искоренению наркотиков в Китае.

Ключевые слова: Китай, Восточная Азия, Шанхай, наркоугроза, наркоконтроль, борьба с незаконным оборотом наркотиков, опиум, синтетические наркотики, наркозависимые, психотропные вещества.

Currently, China acts as the leading power in East Asia, which gives it responsibility for solving important regional problems, which include drug trafficking. It is important to note that this problem directly concerns the PRC itself, since a large number of drug addicts in the country has a negative impact on the further economic development of China.

In addition, China has extensive historical experience in combating drug trafficking. At different historical periods, the leadership of the PRC used various methods to combat drug trafficking. Developing international cooperation in this area at the present stage, China relies on its experience in countering the spread of drugs. As a result, it seems significant to study the evolution of the Chinese approach to combating drug trafficking.

The first cases of China's fight against drugs date back to the 18th century, when in 1729 an imperial decree was passed completely prohibiting the smoking of opium. Subsequently, according to the decree of 1799, the import of opium into the territory of Qing China was prohibited.

However, these measures were not successful for two reasons: firstly, local officials widely condoned opium smuggling, and secondly, the spread of this drug was facilitated by the military intervention of the British Empire during the “Opium Wars”. As a result, the population of the Qing Empire sharply decreased (from 416,118,200 people in 1842 to 369,183,000 people in 1881), and the empire itself entered a semi-colonial state [1].

A further attempt to combat drug trafficking in China was the convening of the International Opium Commission (Shanghai Opium Commission) in Shanghai in 1909 [2].

This event is of particular importance because the convening of this commission was the starting point for the creation of an international drug control system. Thanks to the work of the commission, three years later the first international convention regulating the trafficking of narcotic drugs (primarily the most common drug in that historical period, opium) was signed.

This commission continues to function successfully today. Moreover, in modern conditions, Shanghai often acts as a platform for discussions on various aspects of the fight against drug trafficking.

With the founding of the People's Republic of China in 1949, new, more stringent anti-drug measures were adopted. The “Circular Decree for the Strict Prohibition of Opium and Other Drugs,” signed in February 1950, laid the legal basis for the new government to combat drug use and trafficking [3].

As part of China's anti-drug policy, anti-drug committees were established at the provincial, county, city and village levels to destroy raw materials for drug production, prosecute drug traffickers, and anti-propaganda drug use.

As a result of forced treatment of drug addicts and repressive measures against drug producers (including the death penalty), the number of drug addicts in China was reduced to a minimum. In general, over three years, the state anti-drug campaign has shown its effectiveness, which has convinced China's political leadership of the correctness of applying harsh punishments for crimes related to drug trafficking. The PRC has become a drug-free state for almost 30 years [4].

The problem of drug trafficking has become relevant again in China as a result of Deng Xiaoping's policy of reform and opening up. In the 1980s a system for supplying drugs to the territory of the People's Republic of China was established, which continues to function successfully at the present stage. During the 1980s and 1990s. The problem of drug trafficking was not given due attention, however, by the beginning of the new millennium.

China has realized the importance of this problem in the context of the country's socio-economic development and the need to develop international cooperation in this area, which is confirmed by the adoption of relevant documents and international agreements, which will be discussed below.

Considering the period from 2000 to 2020, it can be noted that the main flow of drugs into China comes from the countries of the Golden Triangle (Myanmar, Laos, Thailand) and the Golden Crescent (Afghanistan, Pakistan and Iran). At the same time, there are small volumes of drug supplies from Nigeria and Tanzania, but in comparison with the previously mentioned exporters, their share is extremely small.

Drugs imported from exporting countries initially enter border provinces such as Yunnan, Guizhou, Guangxi Zhuang and Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Regions, and then spread throughout the PRC [5].

Yunnan Province acts as the largest supplier of drugs from the Golden Triangle to the domestic market [6].

The province of Sichuan plays an important role in the drug supply chain, being a regional center for the redistribution of drug flows.

The natural channel through which drugs are supplied from the Golden Triangle to China is the Mekong River. In addition, the southern provinces of the PRC are often used for the transit of drugs and chemical precursors not only to the Chinese market, but also to other countries [7].

This is facilitated by the presence of a large number of large coastal cities with developed port infrastructure, as well as a network of international airports. The end points of drug trafficking in this case are the USA, Japan and Taiwan [8].

In addition, through the territory of the PRC, drugs enter, among other things, the territory of Russia and the countries of the European Union. The reasons why China has become a promising market for drug trafficking are its high population, growing income levels, and the presence of organized criminal groups in provinces bordering drug-exporting countries.

Heroin remained the most used drug in China in the first decade of the 21st century, but over time the number of addicts using synthetic drugs such as methamphetamine has increased significantly. In the period from 2000 to 2008, in China there was a systematic increase in registered drug addicts from about 860 thousand people, up to 1.2 million people, most of whom used heroin (82% in 2000 and 54% in 2008) [9].

As for the further dynamics of drug use, in 2009 the ratio of drug addicts using heroin and methamphetamine in China was 46% and 42%, respectively, and according to data for 2019, more than 58% of registered drug addicts used methamphetamine and 38% heroin [10].

At the same time, the total number of registered drug addicts continued to grow: in 2010 in China there were 1.5 million, in 2016 2.5 million, which is the peak value for the period studied. By 2019, the total number of drug addicts in China had decreased to 2.1 million people [11].

Moreover, in addition to direct drug consumption, in China since the second half of the 2000s. The production of drugs and their precursors has intensified, and, as a result, their further spread to neighboring countries [12].

Drug manufacturers in China specialize mainly in synthetic drugs, in particular in the production of the previously mentioned methamphetamine, which is due to the presence in China of a large amount of ephedra, a plant that serves as a raw material for the preparation of this drug.

During Deng Xiaoping's tenure, the government's anti-drug model was a harsh policy in which drug suspects were sentenced through mass, fast-track hearings. The result of such sentences, as a rule, was the rehabilitation of the drug addict through forced physical labor [13].

In addition, in 1990, the Anti-Drug Trafficking Regulation was adopted, which not only defines the types of drug-related criminal activities, penalties and compulsory treatment of drug addicts, but also clearly establishes that China has the prerogative of universal jurisdiction over crimes related to smuggling, sale, transportation and production of drugs [14].

This means that citizens of other states may be punished for the above crimes on the territory of the PRC. This resolution has not lost its relevance at the present stage.

Between 2000 and 2020, the PRC repeatedly imposed death sentences on foreigners accused of drug smuggling. Thus, in 2005, a French citizen who was involved in the production and distribution of methamphetamine was arrested and sentenced to death [15], at the end of 2009, the British Akmal Sheikh was executed in China for smuggling 4 kg of heroin, in May 2010 a death sentence was imposed on a Russian citizen who tried to smuggle 2.8 kg of heroin into China [16], in July 2014, the death sentence was carried out against a Japanese citizen for attempting to smuggle synthetic drugs from China to Japan [17].

Among modern cases of death sentences, one can note the conviction of a Canadian citizen for smuggling 120 kg of ketamine in 2020 [18].

In addition to foreigners, capital punishment can be applied to party officials. In this aspect, one can note the relatively recent case of the former secretary of the Boshe village CCP cell, Cai Dongjia, who was sentenced to death in 2016 for drug smuggling and production [19].

Despite an appeal, the sentence was carried out in January 2019. It is worth noting that over time, the Chinese government's approach to the fight against drugs began to change and gradually become more comprehensive. The reason for this was the awareness of the country's political leadership of the extremely low effectiveness of the ongoing anti-drug policy.

Tough methods of combating drug trafficking, which proved effective in the 1950s, did not bring the desired results in the open and economically developing China of the 2000s. This is confirmed by the previously mentioned increase in the number of drug addicts in the country.

In addition, a significant increase in the number of drug addicts naturally led to the spread of HIV. By 2005, drug addicts who inject drugs accounted for 43% of the total number of people infected with HIV [20].

In this regard, in China there has been a need to adopt new legislative initiatives that can respond to modern manifestations of the problem of drug production and distribution. In particular, with the increase in the use and production of synthetic drugs, China has faced the issue of controlling the activities of pharmaceutical companies and drug manufacturers. Moreover, the problem of using narcotic medications for non-medical purposes arose, which also required regulation by the state.

An important document that consolidates the basic principles of the PRC's anti-drug policy is the White Paper on the fight against drugs in China. The document was published in June 2000 and set the goal for the complete eradication of drugs in China [21].

In addition, its text emphasized a prohibitionist approach to solving the drug problem, and the following policy guidelines were formed:

- inclusion of the fight against drugs in the country's socio-economic development program;
- adoption of comprehensive measures to combat drugs, including administrative, legal, economic, cultural, educational and medical;
- continuous improvement of the legal component of the fight against drugs;
- carrying out measures to suppress the use, trade, cultivation and production of drugs, as well as to eliminate sources of drug distribution;
- carrying out anti-propaganda of drug use among young people and adolescents;
- active participation and promotion of international cooperation in the fight against drugs [22].

In addition to these policy guidelines, the White Paper also talks about the importance of effective treatment for drug addicts and control over the circulation of precursor chemicals. The document mentions the flow of illicit substances from the countries of the Golden Triangle as the main external threat to the spread of drugs, while the countries of the Golden Crescent and other sources of drug supply to China are not mentioned at all.

This suggests that the southeastern direction of development of international cooperation against drugs has the highest priority for China. Chinese researcher Su Xiaobo is also inclined to this point of view.

Giving a general description of the White Paper on the fight against drugs in China, it should be noted that this document outlines the main directions of development of the PRC's anti-drug policy, without proposing specific steps for their implementation.

At the same time, the text of the document in an emotionally charged form emphasizes China's successes in the fight against drug trafficking in recent years. This suggests that one of the goals of publishing this White Paper was to create an image of a state that is effectively fighting drug trafficking and emphasizing the importance of China's participation in solving this problem.

Another important document of the PRC, which mentioned the fight against drug trafficking, is the five-year plan for socio-economic development. In the tenth five-year plan for 2001-2005, drug addiction was one of the vices that undermined social stability and was subject to complete eradication.

In the eleventh five-year plan for 2006-2010, the fight against drugs also appears in the section on maintaining national security and social stability. The presence of this problem in the documents defining the socio-economic development of the country indicates its importance for China. The importance of the fight against drugs for China can also be seen in the statements of top officials. In 2005, Chinese President Hu Jintao, at a meeting of the Politburo of the CPC Central Committee, called for a people's war against drugs [24].

This call was largely due to the steady increase in the supply of narcotic substances from the countries of the "Golden Triangle" and, as a consequence, an increase in the total number of drug addicts in the PRC.

Based on statistics on drug seizures in the PRC, a graph was created showing the most common narcotic substances in the period from 2000 to 2010, compiled on the basis of UNODC data. Based on it, one can draw conclusions about which substances were in greatest demand during the specified time period, as well as assess the effectiveness of the activities of Chinese law enforcement agencies in suppressing drug trafficking.

An important event transforming China's approach to combating drug trafficking was the adoption on December 29, 2007 of the "Law of the People's Republic of China on Combating Illicit Drug Trafficking" (came into force on June 1, 2008) [25].

Before its adoption, the "Law of the People's Republic of China on the Control of Medicines", the "Procedure for the Control of Narcotic Substances", the "Procedure for the Control of Psychotropic Substances", the "Procedure for the Compulsory Treatment of Drug Addicts" and the "Procedure for the Control of Medicines Intended for the Treatment of Drug Addicts" were in effect on the territory of the People's Republic of China. "

In general, these legislative initiatives reflected modern trends in combating the spread of drugs, but did not form a general and comprehensive system of legislative regulation of this problem.

The new document was a single legislative act that included all the features of the fight against the spread of drugs and the prevention of drug addiction. According to this document, the National Narcotics Control Committee of the Ministry of Public Security of the People's Republic of China (NDCC MOB) is the main governing body for combating the spread of drugs.

To combat this problem at the local level, it is envisaged to establish anti-drug committees by people's governments, as well as to include the fight against drug trafficking in socio-economic development plans, which involves the inclusion of separate items in the local government budget.

At the same time, the law establishes criminal liability for activities related to the trade and distribution of drugs, while administrative liability is imposed for the use of narcotic substances [26].

An equally important aspect of the new anti-drug law is that drug addiction is no longer viewed as a crime or immoral behavior, but rather as a complex disease requiring comprehensive treatment. Moreover, the law provides for more effective drug addiction prevention, which includes educational activities at various levels, from government organizations to schools and parents of minor children.

Another important aspect of this law is that it established strict state control over narcotic and psychotropic substances that are used for medical purposes [27].

Research activities carried out on such substances were subject to licensing and regular inspection procedures. The importance of controlling possible diversion of precursors from drug production facilities was noted in China's 12th Five-Year Socio-Economic Development Plan, which appears to be related to the increase in the spread of synthetic drugs in the country.

At the same time, in the sphere of regulation of this activity, there is a division of powers between the central government and provincial authorities. In particular, 8 ministries and departments are responsible for the control of pharmaceutical and chemical production and compliance with export requirements in China, which creates bureaucratic obstacles to the timely adoption of necessary decisions [28].

In conclusion, I would like to note that in the period from 2000 to 2020. The approach of the Chinese authorities to combating drug trafficking has changed from methods of tightening penalties for smuggling and distribution of prohibited substances to a comprehensive approach that includes control over medical institutions, preventive and educational activities, as well as rehabilitation and treatment of drug addicts.

One of the problems facing the Chinese leadership has remained unchanged - the spread of corruption in local authorities, which significantly impedes the implementation of promising legislative initiatives. In addition, regulation in the production of chemical and pharmaceutical products has complex bureaucratic procedures, which significantly slows down the decision-making on adding a particular drug to the list of prohibited substances.

The situation with the spread of drugs is also aggravated by the fact that China today has become a drug-producing country. Nevertheless, the decrease in the total number of drug addicts and the volume of seized drugs in recent years allows us to assume, with a certain degree of caution, that the modern anti-drug policy of the PRC has begun to produce positive results.

At the same time, it is important to remember that the main external supplier of drugs to the PRC today remains the countries of the Golden Triangle, which poses the task of developing international cooperation to solve this problem for the Chinese leadership.

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